

Engagement and resistance in an equity-focused professional development: Toward caring with awareness

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Teacher development toward equity should support teachers in seeing the ways in which their practice is part of larger social and political histories and structures so that they can then disrupt oppressive systems influencing students' opportunities to learn mathematics. We examine one teacher's engagement with an equity-focused professional development designed with this need in mind and explore what her experiences suggest about transitions from caring to caring with awareness, explicitly considering race, culture, gender, and power in relation to academic achievement.

Efforts in mathematics teacher education have long emphasized the need to prepare teachers for teaching diverse populations of students in ways that provide equitable opportunities to learn mathematics. However, mathematics education is positioned as part of a larger, neoliberal narrative disconnected from the experiences and realities of students from non-dominant communities (Martin, 2013). Neoliberalism reflects a shift in education from a social to a market concern and contradicts a focus on students' communities, beliefs, and points of view (Lipman, 2012). Teacher development toward equity, then, should support mathematics teachers in seeing the ways in which practice is part of larger social and political structures so that they can then disrupt oppressive systems influencing students' opportunities to learn mathematics.

The Access, Agency and Allies in Mathematical Systems (A3IMS) research project aimed to address these needs, designing and studying a professional development (PD) around five strands: mathematics, discourse, privilege & oppression, culture & community, and action research. Here, we examine one teacher's – Julie's – response to these PD efforts. On one hand, Julie was engaged in the PD and positioned herself as having good relationships with her students and putting students first, always. On the other hand, Julie's engagement was frequently marked with emotive language that suggested dislike and resistance to some PD

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efforts. In short, Julie was a complex participant who challenged us as PD facilitators, showing signs of being a caring teacher but not yet demonstrating caring with awareness (Bartell, 2011), or caring that includes explicit focus on racial, cultural, and political dimensions affecting relationships and mathematics education. We explore the question: *What does Julie's experience with the PD suggest about the transition from caring to caring with awareness in mathematics teaching?*

Background Literature

One long-accepted characteristic of an effective teacher is the ability to cultivate and maintain strong interpersonal relationships with students, often described as caring (Noddings, 1992). Caring is a process; it is something teachers do rather than something teachers feel. Caring relationships between teachers and students lead to higher levels of student engagement and achievement (Pianta, 1999). Mathematical Caring Relationships include teacher's choosing appropriate problems to pose based on students previously demonstrated mathematical reasoning, supporting students' mathematical learning (Hackenberg, 2005). Caring relationships in mathematics classrooms must also reflect *caring with awareness* (Bartell, 2011). Such caring relationships "acknowledge racial identity, culture, racism, and racial privilege as factors that shape and colour experience" (Thompson, 2004, p. 26). For teachers of mathematics, awareness includes an understanding of how mathematics has been used to socially partition individuals by identity markers such as race, gender, and ability. Caring mathematics teachers value and support Students of Colour' status, identity, and prior knowledge and centre issues of race and ethnicity in relationships with students (Rolon-Dow, 2005). Teachers demonstrating *caring with awareness* explicitly reject deficit perspectives of students and their communities. They do not attach mathematical (and other) "failure" to a student, but to themselves, searching within to find a more effective way to reach students (Collier, 2005). They explore students' mathematical thinking and in- and out-of-school experiences to inform changes in classroom practice. These relationships are also political, where mathematics teachers take up "active political stands in solidarity with students and their communities about issues that matter" (Gutstein, 2006, pp. 132-133) and engage students in using and learning mathematics while understanding the world. Teachers demonstrating *caring with awareness* work to ensure that the curriculum reflects the lived experiences of their students, recognize existing oppression in their students' lives, and seek to use their own status to encourage students (and themselves) to understand and undermine those oppressive conditions (Beauboeuf-Lafontant, 2005).

Teachers, and particularly White teachers, often resist discussions of race, culture, and power with respect to teaching and learning. Such resistance can take many forms. Hytten and Warren (2003) identified rhetorical strategies their study participants used in discussions of systemic oppression, including ignoring colour, focusing on progress, victim blaming, and focusing on culture rather than race. For example, people might make statements that suggest people of colour are racist, too, or complain in ways that position White people as

victims in interactions around race. Or people might argue that they “do not see colour,” fuelled by a belief that by ignoring colour, racism is minimized. However, such colour-blind stances allow people to deny that “race, especially skin colour has consequences for a person’s status and well-being” (Rosenberg, 2004, p. 257). It allows White people to dismiss their complicity in racial oppression. This dismissal of complicity is echoed in Annamma et al.’s (2017) expansion of colour-blind ideology where they argue that “colour-blind” is inadequate because it suggests passivity, hides the social construction of race and disability, and ignores the entanglement of these two in oppression. They instead define colour-evasiveness to call attention to the fact that avoidance of discussion about race is deliberate obliteration of the experiences of People of Colour.

It is important to note that many White women have been socialized toward resistance. Women tend to be socialized to avoid conflict (Gillespie et al., 2002). For White women, this avoidance of conflict exists within a social norm that talking about colour or difference is impolite (Mazzei, 2004). Thus, White female teachers [live within] ideologies that expect them to be complicit in the oppression of people of colour because of the expectation of gendered conflict-avoidance and deference. Instantiations of this ideology of the feminine interact with the ideology of colour-evasiveness in a manner that reifies the dominance of White male power and rests it in a space of academic achievement measured in abled ways. Teaching was historically viewed as women’s moral obligation as mothers to raise a child as a productive member of the society (Grument, 1983). Relations of power and authority have historically been formed as patriarchal where teaching is considered both a feminine occupation and a kind of domestic service conducted by women, reifying a “caring teacher is a good teacher” narrative (Apple, 1983).

Method

Thirteen teachers from a small urban district in Granite City, located in the Midwestern U.S., signed up to participate in this PD. All the teachers were women; nine were White and four were African American. Julie is a White, middle-class, heterosexual woman who had taught in Granite City schools for 12 years. She grew up in Granite City but did not attend Granite City Community Schools (GCCS); rather, she attended schools also located in Granite City that she described as “straight down the street.” Julie began teaching in GCCS as a graduate student; her undergraduate degree is in computer science and her graduate degree is in curriculum and secondary education. Most of her 12 years of teaching in GCCS has been at the high school level. At the time of this study, Julie was a math intervention teacher in a school that served grades 7-12.

The professional development

The PD was designed around five interrelated strands as noted above. The *mathematics* strand engaged teachers in mathematics tasks and in adapting curriculum to engage students in inquiry-based tasks and social justice activities. The *discourse* strand highlighted cultural assumptions embedded in expected mathematical discourse and built understanding related

to how these discourse practices contribute to students' positioning and developing identities (Herbel-Eisenmann et al., 2013). The *privilege & oppression* strand gave teachers an opportunity to explore their own racial, gender, class, etc. identities and consider the systemic influence of oppression on mathematics teaching and learning. The *culture & community* strand focused on developing teachers' recognition of the resources for mathematics learning that students bring from their community and cultural experiences. Finally, the *action research* strand emphasized the process of systematically examining, reflecting on, and making important changes to mathematics teaching practices that teachers identified that they wanted to improve. Each year of the PD began with a week-long institute followed by twice-monthly PD meetings throughout the academic year. The first four strands were woven together such that individual activities often reflected the goals of more than one strand (see <https://olemiss.edu/a3ims>). These four strands were the focus of the institute and Fall PD sessions to inform teachers' action research projects in the spring.

Data Collection & Analysis

Any activity that had goals related to the *privilege & oppression* strand or the *culture & community* strand in the first two years of the PD were selected for analysis, representing 81% of PD activities in those two years. All whole group interaction was video recorded and small group discussion was audio recorded. Interviews were conducted with Julie prior to the start of the PD, at the end of the first year, and at the end of the second year. The first interview collected demographic information, teaching history, and asked Julie what she thought equity meant and to describe successes and challenges specific to equity in the mathematics classroom. The final two interviews asked for Julie's reflections on aspects of the PD she found useful, her conceptions of equity and good mathematics teaching, and about tensions that she might be feeling with the dual focus on mathematics and equity in the PD. Finally, at two points during the first year, Julie's teaching was observed, and video recorded and a follow-up noticing interview took place where Julie watched a researcher-selected clip of teaching or student engagement and probed for Julie's thinking about the clip.

To analyse the data, three researchers read through the data set independently and identified three broad codes to look at more closely: Julie's positioning of self, students, and families and communities. We compared our coding and refined codes, resulting in these code descriptions: *Self* focused on Julie explicitly, consciously positioning herself in relation to mathematics, various communities and groups of people or other teachers. *Students* included Julie positioning herself in relation to a particular student as well as to students in her classroom, school, Granite City, and writ large. *Families and Communities* included references to the Granite City community, other cities and school districts, her personal family, and the PD community. The first author then analysed the text within these three broad codes, grouping similar concepts (e.g., Julie talking about an effective teaching practice) into themes. Transcripts were read and re-read for confirming and disconfirming evidence of each theme.

Findings

In our pre-PD interview with Julie, she noted that she enrolled in this PD largely for financial reasons, as she had just purchased a car. At the same time, she was oriented toward this PD as an opportunity to “get involved, to better my practice, to better myself, and to provide for my students.” She had not attended much to the PD goals and aims, perhaps evidenced by her response that what equitable mathematics instruction meant to her was “like an investment, but I don’t know what you mean by equitable.” A moment later, when reflecting on challenges in supporting equitable teaching, Julie said that accountability was key:

If a teacher makes a recommendation, it needs to be followed. If it’s not followed, then the person that didn’t make the change happen needs to be held accountable. Because we’re hurting the student. It’s not about us. It’s not about me...it’s about getting what’s best for that child.

Julie’s assertion that a key feature of her teaching is building strong relationships with students and prioritizing the needs of students was a consistent PD theme.

Strong Relationships, All About the Kids

Julie regularly shared statements across the PD that suggested that she believed she had strong relationships with her students. Prior to the start of the PD, when asked to elaborate on what she meant by getting to know her students, Julie described:

It allows us to have empathy for our students. There may be a student that comes in and is sleeping in class. You don’t know what they went through. You don’t know if they were in the hospital all night. You don’t know if they had to watch their baby brother because Mom had to go to work. When you have those kinds of things happening in your classroom and the administrator comes in and says, “Why is their head down?” you have an explanation because you’re able to show that empathy and understand what the kid is going through. There are times when you may not be doing the curriculum. You may have to stop and talk about those recent shootings in those areas. What if it happens in Granite City?

During the first summer PD, Julie shared stories about students reciprocating care by calling her to see how her mom was doing when her mom was ill and she suggested that she had stronger relationships with her Black students than her White students:

I feel like my Black students will ask more questions than my White students. I don’t know if that is a cultural thing because they feel comfortable talking at home with other people. I mean, I relate better to Black people than I think I do with White people.

During Year 2, after attending a talk with Dr. Jeff Duncan-Andrade, Julie reflected, “I do that on a regular basis. I have that relationship with my students...I’m empathetic. I know that I feel what my students feel. If they’re cryin’, I’m cryin’.” At the end of Year 2, Julie positioned treating students with empathy in relation to culture and race:

I understand that we have cultural issues. We have differences in our lives, and I get that. Every person is different, but just because you are a specific colour, you’re a specific gender, that does not matter. It doesn’t matter because I believe everybody can learn. I don’t think our society believes that, and I think that’s why we talk about social injustice so much, and for me it makes

me angry because instead of talking about it, why aren't we doing something about it. That's what I do in my classroom. I do something about it. I don't look at them because they're Black. I don't look at you because you're Asian. You're a person. I treat you with decency...with humanity, compassion, empathy.

Julie's narrative about having strong relationships with her students was often voiced through her assertion that teaching is "all about the kids." During the first summer, teachers were asked to bring a cultural artifact with which to introduce themselves. Julie shared that she forgot to bring something, but that she knew her artifact was her students. She demonstrated her passionate stance and love for her students with tears:

Since I was in 9th grade, I've struggled with depression...and it wasn't until a few years ago that I ended up going to a therapist...and it wasn't until that, those couple of years ago, that I realized what my purpose in life is. I have such a love for my students (begins to cry), they saved me. They have taught me so much.

Julie also demonstrated a passionate stance about teaching being all about the kids when she shared stories of speaking back to administrators, justifying her teaching and "standing up for what we believe in." During Year 1, for example, Julie expressed a tension between being "pleasers of the government because they pay our paycheck" and education needing to be all about the kids. She elaborated:

It's about what the kids need, about what the kids want, and far too often we push kids on and push kids on and push them on, and they are not where they are supposed to be. It's a growing problem that I don't think our government recognizes. We're limited with you've gotta do this curriculum...you've gotta have this on the board. It's very difficult and frustrating because I just want to come and teach. I wanna be here for the kids. I wanna support the kids. If it takes me two days to go over something because they need that time, then I need to have that freedom, and I don't feel we have that.

In Year 2, Julie continued to stress the importance of instruction being all about the kids, even as she acknowledged that this could be exhausting and demanding: "we may be so burnt out, but we still have a responsibility to those kids...we're supposed to be a friend, confidant, mom, dad...the kids are what is supposed to be our main focus." Julie positioned this stance as standing up to those in power:

We need to stand up for what we believe in. I understand that we are supposed to follow rules and do this and that. I get that, and I'm gonna do that. I'm gonna make sure I get there on time. I'm gonna make sure that I'm teaching my students...If [district mandated curriculum] is not providing my students with the best education, that's where I have to use my professional judgment to modify, to provide those kids with the education they want. I'm not going to provide them a crappy education...it's time we take back our schools, and we take back our classrooms, and we do what we know is best for our kids, no ifs, ands, or buts.

Throughout both years of the PD, Julie asserted teaching as her "mission field" or the place "where I am supposed to be." Julie seems to position her mission not so much about saving students, but about being the best teacher she can be:

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I have always felt that, since I've been involved in my teaching, that this is my mission field. I wanna be the best I can be for these kids, and I can't do that by myself. I need others to support me, to encourage me, to discipline me...to become a better teacher.

This notion of continually growing and working to know her students to “be the best teacher she can be” occurred throughout the PD. At the end of Year 1, Julie reflected:

I don't feel that I know my students as well as I would like to know them. I would like to know what kinds of things they're going through...I feel like they're my children. I feel like I'm like a mom to them. I love them. I care about them. I don't want anything to happen to them. Far too often we don't know our students like we think we do... We had a student who died in a house fire. Did not know he had a sister. Did not know he had a stepbrother here in school. I didn't know that. Here I'm thinking I know the kid, but I really don't.

In Fall of Year 2, Julie again voiced that she doesn't “always know everything they're interested in” and in the Spring of Year 2 that she doesn't:

Have the experiences that they have. I've not grown up in the same kind of culture they've grown up in, so what I think might be relevant may not be relevant for those students. I think there's that big cultural difference. I'm still learning.

Anger Toward and/or Dislike of PD Activities

In some instances, Julie seemed to use the defence of instruction being all about the kids as reason not to engage in politics or assertions of Whiteness. For example, during the first summer she stated:

I'd say about 60 percent of the time, the parents, without finding out the facts, side with the child. Because it's automatic you're out to get them for some reason. I feel like, as a White person, I have that stereotype that I'm going to try to take advantage of a person's colour. That's hurtful to me. Because I love my kids...I will do anything for them.

Later in Year 1, Julie lamented that “people are so political about everything that they forget to think about the kids.” She went on to say:

Even though the district may require something, you can still make it about the kids. It's frustrating to hear how colleagues feel. They're worried about that student evaluation. That's not what you're here for. You're here for these kids. If you didn't meet the expectations...what are you gonna do to improve it? That's how I feel we have to look at it. I think I'm different from how most teachers feel and think, because I want what's best for the kids. It's not about me, it's not about the job, it's about the kids.

Julie also expressed frustration or dislike with PD activities throughout the two years, even if those activities, from our perspective as facilitators, put students first or had the potential to strengthen her relationship with students. For example, in the first summer when provided a handout that listed types of oppression (e.g., racism, elitism, ableism) in Column 1 and then non-target groups (e.g., White people formally educated, temporarily “able-bodied”) and target groups (e.g., People of Colour, informally education, people with disabilities) in the next two columns, Julie immediately voiced:

I can tell you right now I don't like this activity...What I feel when I look at this is division. I feel like, in our country right now, we are dividing ourselves so much already that –I don't look

at these individual – I look at the person as a whole. I don't necessarily relate with everything on here. In racism. I don't necessarily relate better with White people...it makes me angry because I don't feel that we're looking at unifying as a whole.

Similarly, Julie's discussions of race were often points of resistance to the PD activities. For example, at the end of Year 2 Julie noted:

I don't look at their colour, their gender...Yes, they're present, but I don't focus on them because they're a human being that is just trying to find their place in this world. Listening to them I think is the best thing that I can do for them, rather than trying to judge them, or tell them they can do this, or they can do that...[later] I understand that we have cultural issues. We have differences in our lives...but just because you are a specific colour, you're a specific gender, that doesn't matter. It does not matter because I believe everybody can learn. I don't think that our society believes that, and I think that's why we talk about social injustice so much, and for me it makes me angry because instead of talking about it, why aren't we doing something about it?

Julie's resistance was not limited to colour-evasiveness. For instance, in Year 2 after engaging in an activity adapting problem contexts to be more authentic to students' lived experiences, Julie expressed that it "gave me anxiety because our students, I don't focus on the same things our students focus on in culture." She went on to say:

I do see the value in what we're trying to do, but I also see that it is a problem. ... because if we look at how tests are presented to our students, and I'm not saying we need to teach to the test, but if they are not exposed [they'll have more trouble].

This desire of wanting the students to succeed academically as a source of resistance to the PD was inconsistent; while here, during Year 2, she expressed resistance to the activity, at the end of Year 1, Julie noted that although she became frustrated with some of the first-year activities, they were a source of growth/learning:

What I've been learning about myself this year is some of those things that frustrate me the most are the things that are what is making me a better teacher. That frustration turns into memorable moments, powerful moments that help me become the individual that I am. Not necessarily just as a teacher, but as an individual as well.

Discussion

Julie's descriptions of her teaching indicated a caring for her students rooted in ethics and reflected some components of caring with awareness. She is working toward knowing her students culturally, acknowledging difference and race, and recognizing that knowing her students means knowing them beyond the school's walls. Her anger about demands on teachers that she saw as counter to teaching, such as district-mandated pacing, were expressed as care that considered the well-being of the students and could be interpreted as awareness of power structures; she was recognizing that in this realm she can exercise a type of specialized resistance (Collins, 1990). At the same time, in working to know her students beyond school walls, it is not clear that Julie has gotten past "dominant stock stories" (Rolon-Dow, 2005) or that she wanted to know her students well racially. Yet, she also was sometimes

reflective and glad for her growth related to learning about racialized experiences and students' cultures.

Applying a colour-evasive framework (Annamma et al., 2017), we see that the ideology Julie has taken up about race constructs race as an objective difference residing in the individual and does not include an understanding of how race has been socially constructed. Nor does it include the impact of the social and material consequences of racism on her students in their role of student or the educational structures that perpetuate racism. Julie's desire to ignore difference essentializes her students and neglects their complete humanity in favour of only specific parts of their humanity. Julie's belief of herself as a teacher who cares seemed to be a strong part of her identity as a teacher, and so it is possible that facilitating her toward growing the caring relationships to be more aware was felt by her as an attack on an identity she cherished, or even an attack on her students (and their opportunities to learn mathematics). Of note, Julie's assertion that she feels "like a mom" to her students reveals gendered assumptions in her role as teacher, and assumptions about what her students need: the unfit mother is a common stereotype of Black urban mothers in the United States (Gholson, 2016) and so Julie's assertion of taking up that role reifies this storyline. Julie's inconsistent colour-evasiveness made it difficult to know how to support her development from a caring teacher to one who cares with awareness.

Julie's responses in the PD align with documented acts of resistance when White people are confronted with conversations about systemic racism. But her inconsistent gender/colour-evasiveness also suggests that PD could meet her at her points of development and reflection and differentiate activities and experiences to target Julie's particular needs. In Julie's case, perhaps we would have leveraged differently her relationship with her students, having her listen to her students' stories of lived, racialized experiences and using her own students' voices as counter-narratives to her idea that talking about race is divisive and antithetical to caring. Or, instead of focusing on a multitude of intersectional identities, her experiences at some point should have been more narrowly focused on systemic racism, gendered uptake of roles, and their connection to students' opportunities to learn mathematics.

We wonder what it might mean to differentiate PD not only across participants and multiple intersectional identities, but also within groups of participants that share some characteristics (e.g., race and gender) but are at different places in their understanding of the role oppressive systems play in mathematics education. This differentiation likely requires PD facilitators to know their teachers, teachers' contexts, and even teachers' students to support each individual participant toward caring with awareness.

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